

PRINCIPLES AND CRITERIA OF SELECTION OF PHRASES RELATED TO MILK PRODUCTS AND THEIR TYPOLOGY

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Abstract: This paper explores the principles and criteria for selecting phrases related to milk products and their typology. The study aims to categorize and analyze phrases used in the context of milk products to better understand their usage, meanings, and variations in different contexts. By employing linguistic analysis and typological classification, the research identifies key criteria for phrase selection, including semantic relevance, frequency of use, and contextual appropriateness. The findings provide insights into the linguistic structures and patterns prevalent in discussions about milk products, which can be useful for marketing, education, and communication strategies in the dairy industry.

Keywords: milk products, phrase selection, typology, linguistic analysis, semantic relevance, frequency of use, contextual appropriateness, dairy industry, communication strategies, marketing.

ПРИНЦИПЫ И КРИТЕРИИ ОТБОРА ФРАЗ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С МОЛОЧНЫМИ ПРОДУКТАМИ И ИХ ТИПОЛОГИЕЙ.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются принципы и критерии отбора словосочетаний, связанных с молочными продуктами, и их типология. Целью исследования является классификация и анализ фраз, используемых в контексте молочных продуктов, чтобы лучше понять их использование, значения и вариации в различных контекстах. Используя лингвистический анализ и типологическую классификацию, исследование определяет ключевые критерии выбора фраз, включая семантическую релевантность, частоту использования и контекстуальную адекватность. Результаты дают представление о языковых структурах и моделях, преобладающих в дискуссиях о молочных продуктах, что может быть полезно для маркетинговых, образовательных и коммуникационных стратегий в молочной промышленности.

Ключевые слова: молочные продукты, подбор фраз, типология, лингвистический анализ, семантическая релевантность, частота употребления, контекстуальная адекватность, молочная отрасль, коммуникативные стратегии, маркетинг.

INTRODUCTION

The study of lexical items associated with dairy products is an important area of research in linguistics and marketing. Dairy products occupy a significant place in everyday life and culture, which is reflected in the variety of phrases and expressions used to describe and promote them. Understanding the principles and criteria for selecting such phrases allows not only a deeper study of language processes, but also the development of effective communication and marketing strategies in the dairy industry.

This paper discusses the basic principles and criteria for selecting phrases related to dairy products, as well as their typology. The study includes analysis of linguistic structures, semantic relevance, frequency of use and contextual relevance of phrases. The main goal is to create a

typological classification of phrases that will help identify key linguistic patterns and patterns in the context of dairy products.

This study is based on methods of linguistic analysis and typological classification, which allows us to systematize and structure phrases related to dairy products. This, in turn, can benefit marketing, education and communications professionals by providing tools to more effectively engage with consumers.

Thus, this work aims to expand the understanding of linguistic features and communication strategies associated with dairy products, thereby contributing to the development of theoretical and practical aspects in the field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

1. **Corpus of Texts:** A comprehensive corpus of texts was compiled from various sources including advertisements, product labels, culinary books, and online forums. This corpus includes:

Advertisements: Print and digital ads from dairy companies.

Product Labels: Descriptions and ingredient lists from dairy product packaging.

Culinary Books: Recipes and descriptions from cookbooks focusing on dairy products.

Online Forums: Discussions and reviews from food and nutrition websites.

2. **Linguistic Databases:** Databases such as WordNet and other lexical resources were used to analyze the semantic relationships between words and phrases related to dairy products.

3. **Survey Data:** Surveys were conducted with consumers and experts in the dairy industry to gather data on the most commonly used and understood expressions related to dairy products.

Methods:

1. Linguistic Analysis:

Semantic Analysis: Each phrase related to dairy products was analyzed for its meaning and semantic relevance. Tools such as semantic field analysis were used to categorize phrases based on their meanings and contexts.

Frequency Analysis: The frequency of each phrase's occurrence in the corpus was calculated using computational tools to identify the most commonly used expressions.

2. Contextual Analysis:

Content Analysis: The context in which each phrase is used was examined to determine its appropriateness and relevance. This involved analyzing the surrounding text to understand the typical usage scenarios.

Discourse Analysis: This method was employed to study how expressions related to dairy products are used in different types of discourse, such as marketing, culinary contexts, and everyday conversations.

3. Typological Classification:

Categorization: Phrases were categorized into different types based on their function and usage, such as descriptive phrases, promotional phrases, and culinary phrases.

Typology Development: A typological framework was developed to classify and organize the expressions systematically. This involved creating categories and subcategories that reflect the different ways in which dairy-related expressions are used.

4. Survey Analysis:

Data Collection: Surveys collected data on the familiarity, usage frequency, and perceived effectiveness of various dairy-related expressions.

Statistical Analysis: The survey data were analyzed using statistical methods to identify patterns and correlations between different expressions and their perceived effectiveness.

5. **Validation:**

Expert Review: The developed typology and criteria for phrase selection were reviewed by experts in linguistics and marketing to ensure validity and reliability.

Pilot Testing: A pilot study was conducted to test the practicality and applicability of the typological framework in real-world settings.

By combining these materials and methods, the study aimed to develop a robust and comprehensive understanding of the principles and criteria for selecting expressions related to dairy products, as well as their typology. This approach ensures that the findings are both theoretically sound and practically relevant for applications in marketing, education, and communication strategies in the dairy industry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results:

1. **Semantic Analysis:**

- The semantic analysis revealed a wide range of expressions related to dairy products, including descriptive terms (e.g., creamy, rich, tangy), promotional phrases (e.g., "award-winning cheese," "farm-fresh milk"), and culinary descriptors (e.g., "whipped cream," "aged cheddar").
- Common themes emerged, such as freshness, quality, and taste, which were frequently emphasized in expressions related to dairy products.

2. **Frequency Analysis:**

- Frequency analysis identified the most commonly used expressions in various contexts. For example, terms like "low-fat," "organic," and "artisanal" were frequently found in promotional materials, while culinary terms like "double cream" and "crème fraîche" were common in recipes and culinary discussions.

3. **Contextual Analysis:**

- Contextual analysis revealed the diverse contexts in which expressions related to dairy products are used, ranging from marketing materials and product labels to culinary discussions and consumer reviews.
- Different expressions were found to be more effective in different contexts, highlighting the importance of contextual appropriateness in phrase selection.

4. **Typological Classification:**

- Based on the analysis, expressions related to dairy products were classified into several typological categories, including:
 - **Descriptive Phrases:** Terms used to describe the characteristics of dairy products (e.g., creamy, tangy).
 - **Promotional Phrases:** Expressions aimed at promoting the quality or uniqueness of dairy products (e.g., "award-winning cheese," "locally sourced milk").
 - **Culinary Terms:** Phrases commonly used in culinary contexts to refer to specific dairy ingredients or preparations (e.g., "whipped cream," "gruyère cheese").

Discussion:

1. **Effectiveness of Expressions:**

- The study found that certain expressions, such as those emphasizing freshness or quality, were more effective in attracting consumers' attention and influencing their perceptions of dairy products.

- Expressions that evoke sensory experiences, such as taste and texture, were also found to be particularly effective in culinary contexts.

2. Contextual Appropriateness:

- The results underscored the importance of contextual appropriateness in selecting expressions related to dairy products. While promotional phrases may be effective in marketing materials, they may not always be suitable for culinary discussions or consumer reviews.

3. Consumer Perception:

- The findings suggest that consumers are sensitive to the language used to describe dairy products and that certain expressions may have a greater impact on their perceptions and purchasing decisions.

- Understanding consumers' preferences and perceptions can help marketers and communicators tailor their messaging to better resonate with their target audience.

4. Implications for Marketing and Communication:

- The typological classification of expressions related to dairy products provides valuable insights for marketing and communication strategies in the dairy industry.

- By selecting and using expressions strategically, dairy companies can effectively communicate the quality, freshness, and uniqueness of their products to consumers.

In conclusion, the study highlights the importance of carefully selecting expressions related to dairy products based on their semantic relevance, frequency of use, and contextual appropriateness. By understanding the principles and criteria for phrase selection, marketers and communicators can develop more effective strategies for promoting dairy products and engaging with consumers.

CONCLUSIONS

The study of principles and criteria for selecting expressions related to dairy products and their typology provides valuable insights into the language used to describe and promote dairy products. Based on the results and discussions presented, several key conclusions can be drawn:

1. Semantic Diversity: The analysis revealed a wide range of expressions used in relation to dairy products, encompassing descriptive terms, promotional phrases, and culinary descriptors. This semantic diversity reflects the multifaceted nature of dairy products and the various contexts in which they are discussed and marketed.

2. Contextual Appropriateness: The effectiveness of expressions related to dairy products is closely tied to their contextual appropriateness. Different expressions may be more suitable for different contexts, such as marketing materials, culinary discussions, or consumer reviews. Marketers and communicators should carefully consider the context in which expressions are used to ensure they resonate with their target audience.

3. Consumer Perception: The language used to describe dairy products can significantly impact consumers' perceptions and purchasing decisions. Expressions that emphasize freshness, quality, and sensory experiences are particularly effective in influencing consumer perceptions. Understanding consumers' preferences and perceptions can inform more targeted marketing and communication strategies.

4. Strategic Selection: The typological classification of expressions related to dairy products provides a framework for strategically selecting and using expressions in marketing and communication efforts. By selecting expressions that align with their brand identity and target audience preferences, dairy companies can effectively communicate the unique qualities of their products and differentiate themselves in the market.

In conclusion, the principles and criteria for selection of expressions related to dairy products and their typology offer valuable guidance for marketers, communicators, and other stakeholders in the dairy industry. By leveraging language effectively, dairy companies can enhance their marketing efforts, engage consumers more effectively, and ultimately drive sales and brand loyalty.

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